

Feeding habits of Central European candidate vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* on grapevine

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Xylella fastidiosa subsp. *fastidiosa* is a bacterium native to Central America and causal agent of a disease known as Pierce's disease (PD), whose natural spread only relies on xylem-feeding insects. Within Europe, it has been detected for the first time in Mallorca Island, Spain, in 2017. This first confirmation of PD within Europe raised great concern about the risk posed by the bacterium to the European wine industry. A better understanding of the occurrence and ethology of candidate vectors in European winegrowing systems is a prerequisite to develop effective control strategies against a vector-associated spread of *X. fastidiosa* after its introduction into a new environment. Therefore, we aimed at (i) characterizing the insect vectors community in Central European vineyards and (ii) analyzing the probing and feeding behavior of prevalent species in order to decipher differences in the transmission potential of *X. fastidiosa* by these candidate vectors to grapevine. Spittlebugs and sharpshooters represented the most abundant vector candidates in vineyards in Germany. Two spittlebugs whose vector competence has been demonstrated in previous studies, the meadow spittlebug *Philaenus spumarius*, currently assumed to be responsible for all outbreaks detected in Europe so far, and *Neophilaenus campestris*, were the most abundant xylem-feeders within monitored vineyards. In addition, two sharpshooters were occasionally collected on vine shoots, the autochthonous *Cicadella viridis* and the introduced Nearctic *Graphocephala fennahi*. The latter, member of the same genus as the American PD-vector *Graphocephala atropunctata*, is a common sharpshooter species in Central Europe and present on grapevine plants located in public parks and private gardens. We additionally characterized and compared the feeding characteristics of spittlebug and sharpshooter species on grapevine using the EPG (Electrical Penetration Graph) technique. Here we present the main differences in host-insect interaction and their possible reflection on bacterium epidemiology and vector-bacterium relationship.

Keywords: sharpshooters, spittlebugs, vectors